

ISLAMIC ETHICAL FRAMEWORKS ON ASYMMETRICAL WARFARE: LESSONS FROM PAKISTAN'S WAR ON TERROR

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Abstract

In the War on Terror, Pakistan has emerged as a pivotal battleground where traditional Islamic ethical principles confront the realities of modern military strategy. This research delves into the ethical complexities associated with asymmetrical warfare within the Pakistani framework, having particular emphasis on drone strikes, civilian casualties, and the actions of non-state actors. This research employs Islamic ethical concepts, including *adl* (justice), *mizan* (proportionality), *darurah* (necessity), and the principle of *tamyiz* (distinction), to critically evaluate the responses of Islamic morality to the complexities of contemporary conflict. This research employs a qualitative, interdisciplinary approach, integrating case analysis and expert interviews in the fields of religion and military affairs. This research provides a comparative analysis of Pakistan's experience, highlighting the intersections between Islamic ethics and international humanitarian law. The study aims to enhance our understanding of the moral limits that arise in modern warfare and to inform the development of ethically sound strategies for future conflicts.

Introduction

The nexus between the United States (US) and Pakistan in the war on terror exemplified an intricate form of asymmetrical warfare with several significant repercussions. Unconventional threats have challenged traditional military doctrines, while numerous concerns have emerged regarding the implementation of Islamic ethical principles in such conflicts. In contrast to traditional warfare held among states, Pakistan is involved in a battle against non-state entities, including Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP), al-Qaeda associates, and various sectarian militias operating within its frontiers. These groups undermined territorial integrity and contested ideological fundamentals by advocating for the religious justification of violence.

Military operations like *Rah-e-Nijat* (2009) and *Zarbe-Azb* (2014) in the tribal regions of Pakistan, such as South and North Waziristan, raised some significant humanitarian repercussions. The military actions had resulted in the displacement of nearly 1.8 million residents, extensive infrastructure damage, and thousands of casualties of both militants and non-combatants (PIPS 2022, 13-15). State officials put forward an obvious rationale for these measures under the guise of the “doctrine of necessity”. However, questions persisted about the proportionality and targeting of residential areas believed to shelter terrorists. The use of technology, particularly drone strikes executed by the US and Pakistan, has raised complexity. Despite the assistance of Pakistani intelligence in identifying precise targets, collateral damage was recorded. This issue sparked legal and moral objections both nationally and internationally. As Pakistan's foundation was rooted in religious ordinances, religious scholars articulated considerable apprehensions on this matter (Boyle 2013, 2-5).

The Islamic ethical standards have consistently held significance in this discourse. Islamic law provides a framework for action in warfare that emphasizes the sanctity of civilian life, while upholding the principles of proportionality (*mizan*) and justice (*adl*) even in times of war. *Qur'anic* texts like 2:190 (“Fight in the cause of God those who fight you, but do not transgress limits”) have established the outline for the Islamic state to handle violence. Among many jurists, *Al-Shayabani* substantiated the legal manuals of war (*Siyar*) that delineated the fundamental requirements for the treatment of prisoners of war, the protection of women and children, and the safeguarding of civilian property (Khadduri 1966, 60). Despite the fact that the *Siyar* principles are highly regarded in Islamic legal tradition, their enforcement remain limited in the modern Muslim world.

In the context of Pakistan's asymmetrical warfare, these ethical principles might have been compromised. Although religious discourse remained essential to the political and social fabric, its enforcement in military decision-making appear contradictory, especially in terms of the implementation of Islamic norms. Nevertheless, scholars from all Islamic schools of thought issued these *Fatwas*.¹, categorically declaring terrorism, rebellion, suicide attacks, and unauthorized use of *Jihad*² as un-Islamic and illegal under *Sharia* (Dawn 2018). Over 1,800 clerics endorsed it, affirming that non-state actors lack religious authority to wage *jihad* and cannot label state institutions or personnel as infidels (VOA 2018; Rehman 2018). These *fatwas* should have been integrated into strategic doctrines and codes of conduct for the military. Senior personnel of the Pakistan Army publicly defended the ideological foundations of the state, advocating for the supremacy of Islamic principles as the primary framework for handling affairs.

This paper seeks to examine the conflict between normative Islamic ethics and the realpolitik of asymmetric warfare in Pakistan. It assists in ascertaining how the ethical and legal principles deriving from Islamic law have been documented, executed, or disregarded during the years of combating terrorism. The consideration revolves around military actions, taking into account the perspectives of religious scholars and military officers. This study analyzes whether Pakistan's conduct in the war on terror aligns with its proclaimed ideals of International Humanitarian Law. This qualitative research will enhance the broader discourse on the relevance of Islamic ethical principles in contemporary conflict settings, particularly within Muslim states that assert a balance between religious commitments and national security imperatives.

Literature Review and Research Gap

Over the years, Pakistan has been a spearhead in asymmetrical warfare, contending with militant insurgencies, drone operations, and unconventional strategies. This intricate conflict landscape provides a distinctive framework to examine the overarching discussions regarding asymmetric strategies and their ethical implications.

Christine Fair critically analyzes the strategic culture of Pakistan's Army along with its military and counterterrorism strategies. This perspective is essential for comprehending Pakistan's

¹ legal opinion or ruling given by an Islamic scholar on a matter of Islamic law (Sharia).

² It is an Arabic term meaning "struggle" or "striving," often referring to the spiritual, moral, or physical effort in the path of God.

approach to asymmetrical warfare, particularly in relation to its oversight of non-state actors that frequently hinder the enforcement of international humanitarian law. The viewpoint of Fair is crucial as it elucidates how a country's military may rationalize engaging in warfare under the pretext of national security, balancing strategic and humanitarian considerations (Fair 2014).

In their recent paper, Rashid, Majeed, and Ikram (2023) thoroughly analyze the ramifications of drone strikes. They examine its political, social, and psychological impact on the populace of Pakistan. They contend that the implications of the strikes extend beyond their immediate tactical goals. They further explain that how these acts erode governmental legitimacy, exacerbate animosity towards America, and foster the radicalization of the impacted communities? The psychological strain from constant surveillance and the fear of sudden assaults has caused lasting damage to civilian populations (Rashid, Majeed, and Ikram 2023).

Various scholars have emphasized the severity of psychological anguish and the collapse of social values in the context of the current asymmetrical warfare, transcending the boundaries of strategic studies. In the cultural context, dignity is somewhat central to the pursuit of social identity. However, studies such as "Living Under Drones" distressingly illustrate that contemporary war strategies disrupt the social fabric of society (E-International Relations 2015, chap. 3). The doctrine of honorable warfare has been challenged by the evoked intense dread. In these circumstances, the ethical implications of unconventional warfare, especially drone strikes, become increasingly significant, presenting an ethical conundrum. The members of the U.N. Investigative Team assert that drone strikes executed without the consent of the relevant state infringe upon its sovereignty and invoke concerns of distinction and proportionality (Wired 2013). The collateral damage, which is frequently minimized in official reporting, intensifies social animosity and cycles of violence, while further eroding confidence.

Despite their contrasting epistemologies, Ullah and Chishti's analysis confirms that the aims of Islamic just-war traditions and secular ethical norms are aligned. The emphasis on *adl* (justice), *darurah* (necessity), *tamyiz* (distinction between combatants and non-combatants), and *mizan* (proportionality) exemplifies a notable convergence between Islamic ethical discourse and the principles of international humanitarian law (Ullah and Chishti 2024). Joel Hayward's *Violence in the Qur'an* (2012) reinforces this link by examining Quranic texts that restrict the violence (Hayward 2012).

Nevertheless, a matrix of academic research is required due to a significant research gap despite the similarities. Research that seeks to elucidate Islamic ethical concepts in the context of modern military strategy is relatively rare. There is a notable lack of literature examining asymmetric warfare, especially those employing advanced technologies like drones and intricate interplays with non-state actors, through the lens of Islamic principles of *adl*, *mizan*, *darurah*, and *tamyiz*. Moreover, the writings of certain contemporary Islamic scholars who advocate for modernized theology and peace are seldom employed, particularly in the formulation of military doctrines. Indeed, there exists a conspicuous lack of an interdisciplinary framework that converts Islamic ethical principles into practical guidelines for military strategists and decision-makers engaged in asymmetric warfare.

In conclusion, although extensive academic research has been conducted on the strategic, tactical, and ethical aspects of asymmetrical warfare and the Islamic just-war doctrine, there is a noteworthy lack of investigation into the critical intersection concerning the influence of Islamic normative ethics on practical policy and strategy. Bridging this gap would significantly enhance both the ethical considerations of combat in the 21st century and the academic comprehension of the subject.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative approach within a comparative case study framework to examine the ethical aspects of asymmetrical warfare concerning Islamic law and International Humanitarian Law (IHL). Primary Islamic scriptures are reviewed in conjunction with relevant instruments of International Humanitarian Law to evaluate the ethical principles of proportionality, necessity, and the protection of non-combatants, while also asserting and dealing with differences within the ethical doctrines of both fields. To contextualize this theoretical comparison in actual significance, interviews are conducted with three military officers and three Islamic scholars from Pakistan. Participants are permitted to respond to the interview questions on paper or via voice recording. The majority choose to respond in writing. Considering the sensitivity of the issue under discussion, all respondents agree that their identities should remain confidential. The participants' actual names have not been disclosed to preserve their anonymity. This multidisciplinary approach integrates textual analysis with insights from qualitative field interviews, enhancing the understanding of the interpretation and implementation of ethical frameworks in contemporary conflict scenarios.

Conceptual and Ethical Frameworks

Modern asymmetrical warfare necessitates a comprehensive and dynamic ethical framework. This section of the study deals with a normative-ethical framework, employing analysis derived from Islamic legal reasoning through analogy and juristic consensus to ascertain the contemporary ethical challenges of asymmetric warfare. Islamic legal reasoning is based upon the four interrelated concepts: justice (*adl*), necessity (*darurah*), proportionality (*mizan*), and distinction (*tamyiz*)—derived from the *Qur'an* and *Sunnah* and further formulated through *ijma* (consensus) and *qiyas* (analogical reasoning).

From the *Qur'an*, justice is foundational: “Allah commands you to render trusts to whom they are due, and when you judge among people, judge with justice” (*Qur'an* 4:58), and “Stand firmly for justice, even if it be against yourselves or your families” (*Qur'an* 5:8). Necessity allows restricted exceptions: “if one is forced by necessity without willful disobedience, nor transgressing due limits—then there is no sin on him” (*Qur'an* 2:173). Distinction is emphasised in: “Fight those who fight you—but do not transgress; indeed, Allah does not love transgressors” (*Qur'an* 2:190), paralleling the modern principle of protecting non-combatants. The *Sunnah* also corroborates these principles. Classical exegetes highlighted this rule as a foundation for prohibiting aggressiveness and collateral damage, viewing it as a directive for prudence in warfare. The Prophet (PBUH) forbade the infliction of harm against women, children, the elderly, monks, and worshippers (*Sahih Muslim* 19:4320; *Sunan Abi Dawud* 2669). In night raids where civilians were mistakenly harmed, the Prophet stated “they are from them” (*Sahih Muslim* 19:4321-22), underscoring tragic error, not ethical approbation. This statement gently acknowledged the unfortunate reality of accidental civilian harm in a particular historical setting. In today’s context of advanced warfare, where civilian casualties sometimes arise from broader operational decisions rather than unavoidable mistakes, these incidents invite important reflection in light of both Islamic ethical values and international humanitarian principles. However, in the contemporary context, the widespread collateral damage associated with asymmetric warfare and the deployment of advanced military technologies in Pakistan are profoundly concerning, raising critical ethical and legal questions.

Islamic jurisprudence employs the vital legal instruments of *ijma* (juristic consensus) and *qiyas* (analogical reasoning) to preserve ethical continuity and regulate classical values within the evolving arena of modern warfare, especially concerning non-state actors and

advanced technologies such as drones. *Ijma*, originating from the hadith “My *ummah* will never agree upon an error” (Sunan al-Tirmidhi 2166), serves as a regulation for academics to devise a collective resolution to novel issues when the *Qur'an* and *Sunnah* render no guideline. This signifies a compulsory collective moral framework. Vincent Cornell observes that *ijma* allows jurists to adapt archaic principles to the requirements of contemporary conflicts, thereby preserving some element of justice and compassion, albeit transforming tactics and technologies (Cornell 2007, 168). In scenarios such as drone warfare and civilian defense, this collective rationale has been utilized to reinforce concepts such as *tamyiz* (distinction) and *mizan* (proportionality), notwithstanding the unpredictable or ambiguous conduct of militants. This rationale is especially evident in the teachings of the *Hanafi* school.³, dominant in South Asia, which emphasizes public interest and legal flexibility.

Qiyas allows for the application of prior rulings and overarching principles to novel decisions and circumstances. The Prophet's (PBUH) prohibition of poisoned weapons has been extended to encompass contemporary indiscriminate weapons, including nuclear and chemical arms. Additionally, drone warfare has been analyzed through *qiyas* in instances where ethical violations arise from unverified intelligence regarding the target or the collateral damage resulting from the so-called surgical operation. From 2004 to 2014, the United States conducted the most intensive drone strikes in the Waziristan region of Pakistan. These strikes resulted in the fatalities of an estimated several hundred civilian men, women, and children. The consequences of these strikes increased scholars issuing *fatwas*, particularly from the Pakistani Islamic scholarly community, who began to criticize the strikes based on the concepts of *tamyiz* and *mizan*. Analogical reasoning is legitimate solely if new technological innovations correspond to the foundational Islamic principles of proportionality and distinction essential for compliance with *jus in bello* (ethical and legal rules that govern how wars are conducted) standards, including civilian protection and violence restraint (Hashmi 2002, 179-182). *Ijma* and *qiyas* collectively establish a legal philosophy that reconciles the Islamic ethical tradition with the challenges posed by contemporary asymmetric warfare.

The Geneva Conventions, in addition to other treaties, assist in the evolution of international humanitarian law, which is also known as the international laws of armed conflict. The

³ Abu Hanifa was a prominent early Muslim jurist and founder of the *Hanafi* school, known for using reason and analogy in legal interpretation.

International Humanitarian Law (IHL) observes regulations to secure the protection of civilians, the treatment of prisoners on humanitarian grounds, and the imposition of restrictions on the use of weaponry and various strategies. The International Committee of the Red Cross observes that, although international humanitarian law is founded on universal and secular principles, it is frequently associated with Islamic law in the context of protecting human dignity and humanitarian values (ICRC 2018). International humanitarian law (IHL) provides legal frameworks based on treaties that are appropriate for contemporary state systems. Islamic ethics, on the other hand, provides contextual adaptability in conjunction with significant ethical authority, pertinent to a variety of Islamic civilizations. The complexity of current asymmetric warfare needs the development of a framework that is more thoroughly considered. A relevant solution to the gap is the merging of both paradigms that are provided here.

Comparison

Principle	Islamic Jurisprudence	IHL (International Humanitarian Law)
Protection of Non-Combatants	Prohibits targeting women, children, clergy, and civilians (<i>Qur'an</i> 2:190; <i>Sunnah</i> rulings)	Codified in Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols (e.g., Article 51 of API) (ICRC 2025 factsheet) (ICRC)
Distinction	Insists on clear separation between combatants and others (<i>Qur'an</i> 2:190)	A fundamental tenet requires discriminating between combatants and civilians (IRRC 2017 analysis) (International Review of the Red Cross)
Proportionality	Emphasizes restraint and avoidance of excess (<i>Qur'an</i> 2:190; 16:126)	Attack must not cause excessive civilian harm relative to military gain (ICRC factsheet) (ICRC)
Humane Conduct	Mandates ethical treatment of captives, bans on mutilation and looting (<i>Sunnah</i> , classical <i>fiqh</i>)	Mandates humane treatment of detainees (Geneva Conventions, Common Article 3)
Source & Authority	Divine sources with flexibility via <i>ijma</i> & <i>qiyas</i>	Secular, treaty-based law with enforcement via international and state

	(Cornell commentary)	mechanisms (ICRC blog) (ICRC Blogs, ICRC)
Adaptability	Adaptable by analogical application and academic consensus	Developed over the years via treaties and codifications.
Cultural Resonance	Holds strong legitimacy among Muslim communities; enhances compliance	Universally recognized, but local acceptance may vary (IRRC 2024 blog) (ICRC Blogs)

The comparison reveals that while the legal ethics of Islamic law and International Humanitarian Law (IHL) share similar moral foundations, they are also characterized by significant disparities in their origins, interpretations, and application mechanisms. Understanding this convergence facilitates the creation of a principled and contextually adaptable framework for wartime ethics, especially in asymmetric wars. While the ethical aims of both systems often align, Islamic ethics are based on religious law rather than secular agreements. Consequently, what is seen as ethically acceptable in certain Muslim communities is more frequently assessed through a religious lens rather than in relation to international law.

Case Study: Pakistan's War on Terror

In response to the 9/11 attacks, Pakistan deployed troops to the FATA.⁴ (Federally Administered Tribal Areas) region and extended support to the US in the War on Terror. On the other hand, the actions of then-President Musharraf seemed somewhat contradictory, as he granted permission to the Americans to use drones and simultaneously began peace negotiations. Pakistan initiated military operations in 2003 without comprehending the intricately woven tribal dynamics of the region. (Khattaq and Mushtaq 2015, 20).

Despite deploying 7,000 soldiers to South Waziristan in March-April 2004, the military swiftly chose the option of negotiations. Substantial casualties and military desertions convinced them to initiate a peace agreement with Nek Muhammad.⁵ The accord was anticipated to include compensation terms for militants. Consequently, under this unanimously established agreement, militants were expected to cease all hostile actions against

⁴ Former semi-autonomous region in northwest Pakistan comprising seven tribal agencies, merged into Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in 2018.

⁵ The tribal militant commander and founding leader of the South Waziristan Taliban insurgency.

the Pakistani military. The demise of Nek Muhammad in the US drone strike impeded the peace effort. The United States unequivocally rejected this arrangement, believing it would subsequently bolster anti-NATO insurgents in Afghanistan (Muzaffar, Nawab, and Yaseen 2021, 45). The United States criticized Pakistan's efforts to achieve peace through a mutually established accord, prompting then Secretary of State Condoleezza Rice to threaten the cessation of financial aid programs. The peace effort proved futile due to persistent drone strikes that turned FATA into a conflict zone. Following the collapse of the peace deal in 2005, Baitullah Mehsud ascended as the new leader of the TTP, triggering a resurgence of suicide attacks across the country.

To sustain the achievement of operations of the US government in combating terrorism, President Musharraf implemented several measures, including imposing a ban on certain terrorist factions and initiating reforms in *madrassas*.⁶ However, he was unable to impede the expansion of radical organizations, particularly the TTP. Consequently, they scattered throughout the country and dominated the entire region of Bajaur Agency with the assistance of the Afghan Taliban. The military of Pakistan had no alternative solution but to initiate a series of operations in all seven agencies of FATA. They employed both traditional and non-traditional methods to suppress the rebellion. Primarily, they utilized techniques like psychological warfare, targeted assassinations, strategic displacement, and the deployment of tribal militias, sometimes referred to as *lashkars*. However, President Musharraf faced significant backlash from many segments of Pakistan for endorsing US drone strikes. He argued that these attacks were economically viable and had the potential to save soldiers's lives. Conversely, human fatalities from these drone strikes heightened public outcry and intensified regional instability (Irfan, Khan, and Naqvi 2022, 844).

As a result of the 2008 elections, the Pakistan People's Party (PPP) assumed power in Pakistan. The newly elected government confronted a formidable challenge in combating terrorism. They commenced a combination of three strategies: deterrence, development, and dialogue. Notwithstanding the implementation of these steps, the President of the United States instructed the government of Pakistan to execute military operations. In 2009, Pakistan initiated two offensive operations: "Operation *Rah-i-Raast*" in the Swat Valley and "Operation

⁶ Madrassas are Islamic religious schools where students study the Quran and Islamic teachings, though some have been misused by terrorists for radicalization.

Rah-i-Nijat” in South Waziristan. Despite being perceived as a significant military triumph, the leadership of TTP commenced activities from Afghanistan. Drone attacks continue to be a subject of criticism in Pakistan due to the high number of civilian casualties. The UN and Amnesty International asserted that it constitutes a blatant breach of international law and fundamental human rights (Mushtaq and Khattaq 2015, 112).

In contrast to the PPP administration, the government of the Pakistan Muslim League (N) (PMLN) implemented a five-pillar plan comprising the following actions: demolish, confine, prevent, educate, and reintegrate. Considering the concerns about human casualties and violations of international law, the administration refused to employ drone operations. Notwithstanding the implementation of these precautions, a discernible increase in terrorist assaults was observed. The government initiated “Operation *Radd ul Fasaad*” to eradicate the remaining sleeper cells. The launch of “Operation *Zarbe-Azb*” in June 2014 demonstrated the Pakistani military's policy of zero tolerance against the TTP and Al-Qaeda (Syed 2013, 118). The United States, motivated by two primary goals, had been supporting Pakistan's efforts to counter terrorism: the presence of terrorists seeking refuge in Pakistan and the potential acquisition of nuclear technology, which posed a threat to global security. The challenge of addressing terrorism had raised specific ethical difficulties and associated Islamic responses in Pakistan.

Ethical Dilemmas

The drone attacks conducted by the United States had certain implications in accordance with the law of armed conflict (LOAC) and the UN Charter's restrictions. Three conditions must be met for the US-led drone attacks to be justified under Article 51 of the UN Charter: the armed attacks conducted by terrorists, a confirmed connection between the terrorist group and the host state, and evidence of the state's inability to take action against them. The US government's purported provision of self-defense in the case of TTP was untenable due to the lack of evidence establishing TTP's involvement and existence in the 9/11 attacks. Additionally, no evidence was discovered to substantiate any connection between the Pakistani government and TTP. In reality, Pakistan's military engaged in various operations to combat this terrorist group, resulting in significant financial losses and civilian casualties (Shah 2011, 130-132).

Civilian casualties have been consistently identified as a primary concern among numerous social groups, regardless of whether the drone operations were initiated by the US government

or Pakistan. This pertains to the infringement of Islamic principles of *tamyiz* (distinction) and *mizan* (proportionality). Islam delineates certain wartime ethics that emphasize the necessity for the military to distinguish between insurgents and innocent civilians. The safeguarding of civilian lives should be the primary concern during armed conflict. Human Rights Watch research indicated that residences, educational institutions, and places of worship were targeted during drone attacks in war zones such as North and South Waziristan in Pakistan. Statistics revealed that from 2004 to 2013, between 400 and 900 individuals were killed in drone strikes launched by the United States and Pakistan. It is axiomatic that the majority of those killed were women and children (Human Rights Watch 2013, 14-16; Siddiqui 2013, 2). The Pakistani military executed extensive heavy artillery, aerial bombings, and scorched-earth tactics in conflict zones, particularly Khyber Agencies, Bajaur, and North Waziristan, during the operations *Zarbe-Azb* and *Rah-e-Nijat*. That action resulted in the widespread destruction of approximately 40,000 houses and displaced about 570,000 individuals. The airstrikes, based on unsubstantiated ground intelligence, contravened Islamic principles of proportionality and necessity. Such strikes were catastrophic for civilian communities, rendering them unable to obtain healthcare, education, or shelter.

The launch of Pakistan's Burraq UCAV in 2015 marked a significant milestone in the subsequent enhancement of Pakistan's military capabilities. It possessed an autonomous aerial drone system for combat. In contrast to conventional methods of warfare, the use of drones creates a greater emotional and physical dichotomy between the operator and the battlefield, which may contribute to reduced moral engagement and a weakened sense of accountability (Enemark 2011, 224-225). The drone system, possessing disproportionate disastrous capacity, relies more on electronic surveillance and signal intelligence than on human verification. Imprecise airstrikes resulted in numerous civilian casualties (Amnesty International 2015, 21-23; ICG 2017, 13-14).

The outrage among the civil society was exacerbated by actions such as the raid on the village of Angor Ada, which resulted in the deaths of 20 civilians, including children and women. These incidents were documented as the evident violations of international humanitarian law, which may constitute war crimes (Shah 2011, 133). Recently, a drone assault on Hurmuz Village in North Waziristan in May 2025 killed four children from the same family, causing dismay both domestically and internationally (Dawn 2025, 1). The state must address

these recurring incidents in response to growing backlash from civil society. They raised their voice against the extensive use of technology in this warfare, which was conducted without moral guidance. Tribal families, including their elders and children, protested in response to the alleged quadcopter attacks. They held playcards in their hands to express their opposition to the drone strikes.

The protection of women and children during drone attacks was undoubtedly violated, as the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) explicitly instructed that their safety must be guaranteed during times of conflict. This violation underscored the disregard for fundamental Islamic legal and ethical principles, including *tamyiz* (distinction) and *adl* (justice). The principle of *darurah* (necessity) must be taken into account in the context of war to regulate the use of military technologies, including drones. Moreover, the psychological terror and excessive harm inflicted upon civilians compromise the Islamic concept of *mizan* (balance). The principle of *tamyiz* was also undermined by the inability to differentiate between legitimate military targets and innocent people during such assaults.

In Balochistan and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, particularly, enforced disappearances, illegal detentions, and military tribunals without due process have been extensively documented during Pakistan's War on Terror (International Court of Justice 2020, 45). These procedures are contrary to Islamic jurisprudence and international humanitarian law (IHL), which prioritize justice (*adl*) in the context of warfare (Rehman 2007, 140; Malik 2020, 24). In the same vein, the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols explicitly prohibit the intentional targeting of civilians, as outlined in IHL. These incidents exhibit ethical tensions: although they are justified as necessary for national defense, they frequently violate the IHL principle of distinction and *tamyiz*, which raises concerns about accountability.

However, the statistics indicated a clear decrease in the number of drone attacks that resulted in the deaths of innocent people. This was primarily due to the enhanced precision of the targets (Becker and Shane 2014, 6). However, Amnesty International underscored the importance of accountability by considering specific attacks as war crimes (Greenwald 2013, 2). A 2012 Pew Research Center study revealed that 94% of Pakistanis believed that the assassination of a significant number of civilians reinforced the pervasive criticism (Pew Research Center 2012). The locals perceived these drone attacks as dishonorable, which resulted in social and psychological damage that could potentially incite a series of retaliation

(Markus Markert 2015). Although the military operations succeeded in shaking the terrorist bastion, such instances of moral oversight left profound scars on the impacted communities. Drone attacks have been severely denounced by religious scholars, especially in Pakistan and other Muslim countries, who contend that the high number of civilian casualties breaches both international humanitarian law and Islamic ethical norms. They stress that attacking non-combatants damages public confidence in international rules and calls into question the morality of war (Reprieve 2012). The perceived dilemmas in the context of asymmetrical warfare in Pakistan will be better understood through the responses of concerned persons, such as religious scholars and army personnel.

Analysis of Interview Data (Responses of Religious Scholars)

Three eminent Islamic scholars have been interviewed, and their responses are systematically analysed in the following section. In order to ensure confidentiality, the participants are identified as follows: Respondent 1 is an expert in *Sharia* with a doctoral degree; Respondent 2 is skilled in Islamic jurisprudence (*Fiqh*) and has a PhD in *Sharia*; and Respondent 3 is in charge of Islamic Studies and Coordinator of the *Fehm-ul-Quran* program at renowned university of Lahore. The analysis is predicated on the Islamic jurisprudential concepts of *adl*, *mizan*, *ḍarurah*, and *tamyiz*, which are essential to this study. It addresses emerging themes related to the Islamic ethics of contemporary warfare.

1. Ethical Pre-conditions for War

All respondents believe that warfare is ethically permissible in Islam solely under severe conditions, especially in defensive scenarios. Based upon the *Qur'anic* verses (e.g., 2:190, 4:75), they emphasize that warfare should be a final recourse, sanctioned when a peaceful alternative, such as negotiation, agreements, or mediation, has proven ineffective. Respondent 1 highlights the necessity of informing the opponent before initiating warfare, in accordance with traditional Islamic principles.

This illustrates Islam's focus on moral moderation, wherein conflict must pursue legitimate objectives such as safeguarding human rights and reinstating peace, rather than expansionism or vengeance.

2. Islamic Ethical Principles in Warfare

The Respondents acknowledge the fundamental challenges of contemporary conflicts. They view these four elements as essential to Islamic *Sharia* ethics.

Justice (*Adl*): The conduct of warfare must be just regarding its rationale and execution; Respondent 3 clarifies that justice is delivering what is deserved, nothing more. This principle must remain essential even during combat.

- **Proportionality (*Mizan*):** All respondents underscore that the magnitude of retaliatory military actions should correspond appropriately to the perceived danger. The unjustified use of force during the war, which could lead to unnecessary destruction, is prohibited.
- **Necessity (*Darurah*):** under certain circumstances, military operations are deemed indispensable. Respondent 2 justifies war as the means solely to prevent further loss. A country must rationalize its decision to engage in warfare if the anticipated harm outweighs the probable benefits
- **Distinction (*Tamyiz*):** The experts's categorical condemn the harm inflicted upon non-combatants, especially civilians, women, children, and non-military targets. They emphasize the necessity of strict compliance with the extensive regulations of combat mandated by *Sharia*.

The respondents's perspectives on this matter are closely aligned with Islamic legal principles, which also intersect with international law and regulations governing warfare.

3. Legitimacy of Pakistan's War on Terror

The expert's approach is critical in examining Pakistan's position in the US-led War on Terror. Respondent 1 and Respondent 2 advocate for conditional involvement, underscoring that activities should be anchored on ethical norms rather than political coercion.

Respondent 3's comment is more profound, expressing concern regarding partnerships with foreign entities whose goals may conflict with the principles of Islam. An agreement arises among scholars that counterterrorism is essential, but it must be state-led, transparent, and ethically structured. The collaboration must uphold Islamic principles and the nation's sovereignty.

4. Use of Drone Technology

The ethical ramifications of drone warfare are quite a grave matter. Scholars endorse surveillance drones with reservations, although they maintain a more circumspect position about lethal drone strikes. Respondent 1 states that it is deemed unethical when conducted without prior warning or if it causes disproportionate civilian casualties.

Respondent 3 resembles drones to bows and arrows by analogy, but he emphasizes that the significantly greater destructive capacity of drones demands precision and responsibility. The drone strikes are deemed acceptable alone under strong ethical criteria aligned with *tamyiz and mizan*, underscoring the need for rigorous doctrinal frameworks to assess modern technologies.

5. Civilian Protection and Collateral Damage

All interviewees unanimously assert that civilian casualties must never be normalized or perceived as an unfortunate byproduct of warfare. Respondent 1 acknowledges that collateral harm can be acceptable in severe circumstances, but the loss of many innocents to apprehend a single militant is unjustifiable.

Respondent 2 argues that the military operation becomes ethically and spiritually repugnant when the anticipated benefits are outweighed by civilian casualties. At present, Islamic ethics firmly protect the lives of non-combatants, which requires a re-evaluation of modern warfare strategies in accordance with these principles.

6. Authority to Declare *Jihad* and Role of Non-State Actors

All academicians categorically reject the assertion made by non-state actors, such as the Tehrik-i-Taliban Pakistan (TTP), regarding the religious legitimacy of violence. It is generally agreed that only a legitimate Islamic state has the authority to declare a *jihad*.

Respondent 3 also states that the resolution of grievances against the state should be addressed via legal protest and reform, rather than violence. These viewpoints contribute to the escalating delegitimization of militant insurgencies, which are frequently concealed under the guise of *jihad* to achieve their pernicious objectives.

7. Inclusion of Scholars in Decision-Making

The absence of substantive consultation with Islamic scholars regarding the state's military policy is identified by all three respondents. Scholars are rarely consulted on matters of national security and warfare, despite the existence of the Council of Islamic Ideology in Pakistan.

This pattern suggests a policy vacuum in Islamic law and a common desire for the systematic involvement of Islamic scholars in policy formulation and planning.

8. Jurisprudential Adaptation: *Ijtihad, Ijma, and Qiyas*

Interviewees underscore the importance of interpretive renewal in Islamic jurisprudence for the most recent warfare strategies. The use of *ijtihad*⁷ and *qiyas* for the rulings regarding drones and cyber warfare is endorsed by Respondent 1 and Respondent 2.

Respondent 3 views the renewal of the *tajdid*⁸ as an enduring scholarly obligation, emphasizing that the new forms of war, like other new domains, necessitate an assessment of *Sharia*-compliance. This particular concept demonstrates the capacity of Islamic legal reasoning to ethically accommodate new forms of warfare, irrespective of their complexity, without abdicating fundamental principles.

9. Codifying an Islamic Manual of War Ethics

The drafting of an Islamic ethical guide to warfare in its most codified form is actively supported by all scholars. A resource of this nature can serve as a guide for armies in Islamic countries, safeguard Islamic values from distortion by non-state Islamic groups, and clarify the principles of *jihad*, civilian protection, and the use of modern technologies in warfare.

Respondent 3 is the most delighted to be involved in framing the undertaking as a sacred scholarly obligation.

Analysis of Interview Data (Responses of Military Personnel)

This theme analysis integrates the viewpoint of three officers of the Pakistan Army regarding the understanding and resolution of an ethical dilemma in the course of warfare, focusing specifically on the conduct of the soldiers within the framework of Islamic ethics. Respondent 1:

Oversaw operations through a Forward Traclement Center in South Waziristan and held a command-level position; involved in strategic planning rather than direct combat.

Respondent 2:

Commanded a company-sized combat unit engaged in security, surveillance, and counterinsurgency operations; focused on minimizing civilian harm and following ethical protocols. Respondent 3:

Worked in intelligence gathering in Waziristan; involved in identifying militants, supporting

⁷ It is the process of independent reasoning by qualified scholars to derive legal rulings from Islamic sources in the absence of clear texts.

⁸ It refers to the Islamic concept of religious renewal or revival, aiming to restore the faith to its original purity and relevance.

operational planning, and managing local community awareness. This analysis is organized around five major themes emerging from their responses. Each of the themes deals with the moral aspects of the ongoing conflict in the context of the Pakistan War on Terror, especially in relation to the Islamic ethical viewpoint.

1. Ethical Military Training and Religious Foundations

All three respondents highlight that military training in Pakistan incorporates elements of Islamic ethical rules of warfare. This encompasses refraining from killing innocent individuals (particularly women and children), preventing the damage of public property, and participating in combat solely under justifiable circumstances. Respondents 1 and 2 specifically reference the Islamic norms of warfare as imparted by the Prophet Muhammad (PBUH), which are reflected in modern military briefings and unit-level training before deployment in war zones.

Respondent 2 provides a compelling illustration of relinquishing tactical advantage to adhere to these principles, opting not to check a burqa-clad terrorist, who subsequently detonates a destructive device, based on the assumption of her being a civilian woman. This incident highlights the ethical implications of following moral rules in situations.

2. Civilian Protection and Rules of Engagement

A prominent repeating theme is the dedication to reducing civilian losses, notwithstanding the asymmetric character of the combat. Respondent 2 underscores a zero-tolerance attitude regarding collateral damage, clarifying that civilians were relocated to Internally Displaced Person (IDP) camps to prevent injury. Respondent 3 emphasizes that the relocation of innocent individuals is prioritized during operations. Respondent 1 provides a more analytical viewpoint, highlighting that a 2:1 ratio (two militants for every one civilian) has been employed in high-risk judgments, suggesting the ethical considerations that arise when collateral harm is unavoidable. This illustrates the challenging ethical decision-making required in active warfare, albeit not optimally.

All three responses underscore that Islamic values, international humanitarian law, and military procedures intersect in formulating rules of engagement.

3. Identifying Combatants and Operational Challenges

A prevalent ethical dilemma acknowledged by all interviewees is the problem of differentiating between militants and civilians. In the tribal regions, strong ethnic and cultural affiliations enable militants to seamlessly integrate with the local populace to disguise their presence

among civilians. Respondent 2 articulates that militants utilize the garb of women and children as shields to avoid detection, raising operational limitations and ethical quandaries.

Respondent 3 explains that the identification process is both protracted and intricate, with any inaccuracies potentially leading to operational and ethical ramifications. This very issue highlights the strain that asymmetrical warfare places on state military, particularly those who exhibit ethical conduct.

4. Islamic Values in Operational Decision-Making

All interviewees acknowledge that Islamic moral precepts continue to influence the operational decisions of the officers; however, their application based upon the context and the degree of intelligence certainty varies. Respondents 2 and 3 assert that drones or other kinetic activities are permissible solely where there is accurate, verified intelligence and the ethical requisites are met.

Respondent 1 offers a comprehensive analysis of geopolitical considerations, including Iran's influence, that affect the adoption of specific technologies such as drones.

This indicates a more pronounced ethical dilemma that intertwines Islamic values with geopolitical strategies, wherein decisions are shaped by Islamic ethics and national security imperatives. The respondents unanimously denounce the endeavors of non-state actors attempting to rationalize violence in the name of Islam, asserting that such actions are misrepresentative and contravene the principles of Islam. Respondents express concern about how these individuals have exploited ignorance and antiquated social customs to attract and radicalize youth.

5. Use of Technology and Ethical Boundaries

Emerging technologies, such as drones and surveillance systems, are perceived as essential; nonetheless, they entail significant ethical dilemmas. Respondent 2 asserts that surveillance is confined to military targets and strategic pathways, therefore reducing infringements on civilian privacy.

Respondent 3 acknowledges that privacy may be compromised, but solely in situations when terrorists utilize civilians as human shields.

All respondents recognize that the implementation of such technologies necessitates rigorous ethical examination, rooted in Islamic military principles and state legislation. There appears to

be a consensus that Islamic jurisprudence must evolve to offer direction and establish clearer regulations regarding the use of contemporary warfare systems.

Results & Discussion

Interviews with military officers and religious scholars reveal a convergence of ethical concerns regarding war in Pakistan, particularly pertaining to its regulations rooted in Islam. Both groups emphasize the importance of justice (*adl*), proportionality (*mizan*), necessity (*darurah*), and distinction (*tamyiz*) as fundamental primary principles in the assessment and execution of any warfare and its strategies. Despite the fact that religious academicians provide a jurisprudential foundation for these principles, military officers contemplate their enforcement in practical situations, notably in the context of Pakistan's war on terrorism.

The safeguarding of civilians has become a prominent ethical imperative. Religious academics dismiss any justification for civilian losses, regardless of the severity of the situation. Officers emphasize the systematic endeavors to rationalize such harm, encompassing, but not restricted to, structural evacuations and rigorous rules of engagement standards. Notwithstanding these precautions, the officer remarked on the almost insuperable difficulty of controlling collateral damage in asymmetric warfare. They highlight the fact that the operational and ethical dilemmas of the situation are further underscored by the complexities of detecting militants when terrorists intentionally disguise themselves in civilian apparel or camouflage themselves among the locals, presenting themselves as tribal family members.

Additionally, both groups of respondents share concerns about the moral constraints established by emerging technology, especially drones and surveillance. Scholars advocate for the revitalization of *ijtihad* and *qiyas* to establish Islamic rules on the matter, while the officers support these instruments, contingent upon precise intelligence and proportional application. All responders unanimously agree that these new technologies must be employed within strict ethical constraints, aligned with Islamic teachings and international law. Both academics and officials concur on the exclusion of non-state entities from the Islamic context, asserting that only an Islamic state can legitimately ascribe the word '*jihad*' to an activity. This issue, expressed by both parties, focuses on the use of Islam by counter-violent groups to justify their actions, prompting both parties to stress the necessity of grassroots initiatives to undermine these narratives.

There is a notable deficiency identified in the participation of Islamic scholars in state-level military decision-making. Although the officers acknowledge the significance of Islamic morality and ethics in training and conduct, there is no evidence of any systematic institutional frameworks capable of integrating intellectual counsel into operational strategy. This gap underscores the absence of formal procedures that enable ethical and religious oversight in defense strategies. In response to the development of combat technology and the emergence of new spheres of conflict, both religious academicians and military personnel demonstrate a willingness to adjust to jurisprudential change. *Tajdid*, or “renewal”, is considered a religious obligation by scholars, while its practical importance in the successful justification of moral decision-making in contemporary contexts is acknowledged by officials.

In summary, the findings suggest that religious legal ethics and military conduct are primarily in accordance despite the presence of some structural discrepancies and gaps between theory and practice. There is a dire need for collaboration to establish a codified Islamic manual on Islamic military ethics that addresses classical and modern challenges. This manual will comprise the potential to safeguard operational integrity, reduce ethical violations, enhance the moral legitimacy of state-sponsored counter-terrorism, and prevent the misuse of Islamic doctrine by non-state actors.

Conclusion

This research demonstrates the relevance and adaptability of the principles of justice (*adl*), proportionality (*mizan*), necessity (*darurah*), and differentiation (*tamyiz*) from Islamic ethics to address the ethical challenges posed by asymmetrical warfare. This study analyzes the ethical frameworks established within the context of Pakistan's war on terror. The case study of Pakistan further substantiates the efficacy of jurisprudential *ijtihad* and *qiyas*, which offer interpretive flexibility in tackling contemporary concerns such as drone warfare, civilian protection, and the participation of non-state actors. The research emphasizes a convergence between the practical concerns of military personnel and the normative commitments of Islamic scholars, all of whom recognize the importance of protecting innocent individuals and adhering to ethical constraints, even under the pressure of military operations. Nevertheless, the gap between Islamic ideals and military praxis is underscored by recurring ethical violations, including indiscriminate drone strikes, disproportionate force, and a lack of accountability.

Furthermore, while upholding the moral precepts of war, Pakistan's cooperation with other nations, particularly the US, has made the situation more complicated. Such a collaboration aids Pakistan in implementing the latest warfare strategies, including intelligence sharing, targeted executions, and drone operations. No doubt, this partnership has increased the ability of Pakistan's military to carry out complex operations, but it may create problems in adhering to Islamic military norms. These conditions raise concerns about state accountability, state sovereignty, and the validity of contemporary military strategies within the framework of Islam. Foreign power's involvement diminishes accountability and increases the possibility of civilian casualties, further undermining the legitimacy of the legal and religious frameworks.

The formalised Islamic code of ethics for warfare, even as suggested by Islamic academics and military professionals, is a vital necessity of the present era. Its absence makes it difficult to address the problems associated with contemporary asymmetrical warfare. The Pakistani military's decision-making process readily evaluated the gap between theory and practice. The necessity for a hybrid moral-legal framework rooted in both tradition and modernity is demonstrated by lessons learnt from Pakistan. Islamic law is unquestionably a comprehensive source of instruction, but in order to solve problems like terrorism, guerrilla and remote warfare, and artificial intelligence, it has to be reinterpreted. Combining IHL ideals with Islamic jurisprudential ethics could create a morally sound and culturally resonant foundation. This convergence may prove to be a prudential corpus of policy for asymmetric warfare ethics in the 21st century.

The importance of a dynamic and contextualised interpretation of Islamic ethics in developing a military code of conduct is demonstrated by this study. A codified manual of war ethics will also help deal with one of the crucial issues of the misinterpretation of Islamic ideology by non-state actors. States with a majority of Muslims must be urged to closely examine their own moral and strategic obligations. This work adds to a larger, more principled moral discourse on the ethics of war in the modern day by integrating Islamic ethical precepts into contemporary security contexts.

Based on the findings, the following practical and policy-relevant recommendations are proposed:

- Create an Islamic ethical framework (based upon the reinterpretation of traditional principles) for contemporary combat to address the problems of non-state militancy, drone strikes, and civilian losses.
- To avoid outrage, military strategy practitioners should base decisions regarding war only on principles derived from *Sharia* and IHL obligations.
- Strengthen monitoring and accountability systems for military operations that include civilian casualties and cooperation with foreign intelligence.
- Create a multidisciplinary panel of Islamic scholars, jurists, and military strategists to offer advice on moral conundrums in combat.
- Increase the effectiveness of current oversight systems for military operations with foreign partners.
- Pakistan should cautiously engage in foreign counterterrorism efforts to avoid sovereignty breaches and civilian harm.
- Utilise Islamic values to refute radical interpretations and undermine militant organisations' deceptive religious practices.
- To establish coherent religious and international guidelines for the conduct of war, combine Islamic ethics with international humanitarian law.

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